

**Investigation on Structural, Optical and Room Temperature Dilute Magnetism
in Nanoscale Co and Fe co-doped SnO₂**

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Abstract:

SnO₂ nanoparticles exhibiting room temperature ferromagnetism (RTFM) have been prepared by citrate gel combustion method. The saturation magnetization (M_s) of the nanoparticles experiences an increasing trend with an increase in Co and Fe dopant concentration. The annealing temperature also affects the oxygen vacancies which is also responsible for the origin of the Room Temperature Ferromagnetism. The structural, surface morphological, optical and magnetic studies were carried out using XRD, FESEM, UV-vis-NIR spectroscopy, photoluminescence and VSM. The tetragonal rutile structure of SnO₂ was confirmed using XRD data and it was found that this structure was not affected by Co and Co:Fe co-doping. It was observed that the magnetization increased with Co doping whereas decreased marginally after Co:Fe co-doping. The bound magnetic polarons resulted from the oxygen vacancies play a key role in the observed room temperature ferromagnetism.

Keywords: Diluted Magnetic Semiconductors, Room Temperature Ferromagnetism, BMP

References:

1. Agrahari, Vivek, et al. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 622 (2015): 48-53.
2. Mounkachi, O., et al. *Materials Letters* 134 (2014): 272-275.
3. Fu, Yuting, et al. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 698 (2017): 863-867.
4. Nilavazhagan, S., and S. Muthukumaran. *Superlattices and Microstructures* 83 (2015): 507-520.